

The Influence of Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, Ancillary on Interest in Visiting the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque Solo Religious Tourism

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Abstract:

This research aims to determine the influence of Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, Ancillary (4A) on the number of tourist visits and correlation between 4A factors in attracting visitors to come to the Sheikh Zayed Mosque, Solo. In this research, the field research method was used, using a descriptive approach that systematically describes the facts that occur in the field. This research method was observation, interview and documentation to collect data. This research was conducted for 20 days, while data analysis used deductive analysis. The results of this research show that the influence of 4A factors is very large on the number of tourist visits to the Sheikh Zayed Mosque, Solo. The beauty of the architecture and design of the mosque (Attraction) which combines local cultural elements with Arabic architectural style is the main attraction that influences tourists' interest in visiting. Strategic location and facilities that make it easier for visitors, also increases the number of visits, with easy access for Muslim and non-Muslim tourists (Accessibility). The facilities provided by the Sheikh Zayed Mosque (Amenities), such as the ablution room, VIP room and Islamic Center, provide comfort and support religious and social activities for visitors. Apart from that, supporting services (Ancillary) such as Islamic study activities, fasting together, and congregational prayers during the month of Ramadan also increase visitors' interest in coming.

Keywords: Accessibility, Amenity, Ancillary, Attraction, Sheikh Zayed Mosque.

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Introduction

Tourism is an activity of visiting a temporary place for various specific purposes, both group and individual visits. Tourism is one of the largest and fastest-growing sectors globally, contributing significantly to economic and cultural exchange. In Indonesia, with its vast diversity, tourism plays a pivotal role in promoting cultural heritage and economic development.

Indonesia's tourism offerings are as diverse as its culture, encompassing cultural, religious, and natural attractions. These destinations, rich in history and beauty, position Indonesia as a global tourism hub, as well as a million other beauties that can be enjoyed. The tourism sector is an important factor in the progress of a place. Because if tourism advances and develops, then other sectors will also develop, such as the economic sector and the human resources sector.

Solo is renowned for its rich cultural and religious heritage, offering diverse attractions that draw both local and international tourists. Among these, the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque stands out as a newly inaugurated icon of religious tourism, celebrated for its architectural grandeur and spiritual significance. One of the religious tourist attractions in Solo is the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque in Solo, which was recently inaugurated as a religious tourism icon, attracting widespread attention because of its architectural splendor which combines modern design and Islamic traditions. The presence of this mosque is not only as a place of worship, but also as a religious tourist attraction that offers strong historical, cultural and spiritual value. Since it opened, this mosque has succeeded in becoming a major attraction that attracts visits from local and international tourists, strengthening the potential of the city of Solo as a religious tourism destination

Several factors that influence tourists' interest in visiting religious tourism destinations, including the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque, can be seen from four important elements: Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, and Ancillary (Rahmawati; 2022). The first factor, Attraction, includes aesthetic aspects and the spiritual meaning of the mosque which is able to create a deep impression on visitors. Research shows that visual and cultural attractions are often the main motivation for tourists in choosing a destination (Pratama; 2021)

Second, accessibility or ease of access is an important aspect in developing tourist destinations. The location of the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque which is easy to reach, both by public transportation and private vehicles, really supports better accessibility for tourists. Studies show that good accessibility can significantly improve visitor comfort and increase the number of visits.

Third, amenities or supporting facilities around the mosque, such as parking areas, places to eat and other public facilities, also contribute to providing a comfortable tourist experience for visitors. Providing adequate facilities is an important factor in influencing tourist satisfaction

Finally, ancillary or additional services, such as tour guides, providing historical information, and regular religious activities, play a role in enriching the visitor experience. This service provides added value that can increase visitor loyalty and encourage them to return to visit.

By considering the influence of these four factors, it is hoped that the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque can increase its role as a sustainable religious tourism destination. This research is important to evaluate the extent to which Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, and Ancillary influence tourist interest, so that more appropriate development strategies can be implemented to maximize tourism potential in the future.

Based on the background discussed, this study aims to examine how the 4A factors (Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, Ancillary) influence the number of tourist visits to the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque. Additionally, it seeks to explore the interrelationships between these factors in shaping visitors' interest. What is the relationship between Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity and Ancillary factors in attracting visitors to come to the Sheikh Zayed Mosque, Solo.

Research Method

This research is field research using qualitative methods at the Sheikh Zayed Mosque, Solo, located at Jalan Ahmad Yani No. 128 Gilingan Village, Banjarsari District, Surakarta City. This research involves collecting and analyzing qualitative data, which is presented in a descriptive narrative format. This research describes data in the field and is presented using written words related to the data influence of Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, Ancillary (4A) on the number of tourist visits and correlation between 4A factors in attracting visitors to come to the Sheikh Zayed Mosque, Solo. This study adopts a descriptive qualitative approach, which involves systematically documenting and interpreting observed phenomena to uncover patterns and insights (Mardalis, 2006). The data collection method in this research uses observation, interviews and documentation. The approach taken is to use a descriptive approach, meaning that this research systematically describes the facts that occur in the field. The data sources in this research are divided

into two, namely primary data and secondary data. Primary data was collected directly from stakeholders, including mosque visitors and management, through interviews and observations. Secondary data consisted of supporting literature, such as tourism-related studies and official mosque documents (Joko Subagyo 2015).

Related Work

Related research is a brief description of the results of previous research on similar problems with related titles, which functions as authentic data regarding the authenticity of the research. Based on observations made by the author. So far there has been no research that discusses the Influence of Attraction, Accessibility, Amenities, Ancillaries on Interest in Visiting the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque, Solo, Religious Tourism. However, the author found research that is similar to the research that will be carried out. It is hoped that the research that will be carried out by careful researchers can add to the body of knowledge.

A similar article by careful researchers is an article prepared by Ajis Subhan and Muthoifin, Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta in 2024. With the title *The existence and effectiveness of the Sheikh Zayed Solo Grand Sharia Mosque tourism*. This research is descriptive research that uses qualitative analysis. Data collection in this research was carried out by observing, interviewing and documenting. The results of this research show that the Sheikh Zayed Solo Grand Mosque is not yet effective as a sharia tourism and is still far from being called Sharia Tourism because the Sheikh Zayed Solo Grand Mosque sees the absence of several supporting factors such as halal food and drinks/halal culinary, accommodation factors such as sharia hospitality. around the mosque, factors such as travel agencies that have not been provided, and the absence of tour guides who work in accordance with the Sharia Tourism SOP.

This article was prepared by Dena and Gusti Agung from the Undergraduate Tourism Study Program, Faculty of Tourism, Udayana University. With the title *"4A Tourism Components (Attractions, Accessibility, Facilities, Additional) in the Gunung Payung Cultural Park Tourist Attraction"*. This research uses qualitative data collected through observation, interviews, documentation, and study literature. The data in this research was analyzed using qualitative descriptive techniques or creating descriptions in narrative form based on the qualitative data obtained. The results of this research are in the form of an explanation regarding the availability of 4A tourism components in the Gunung Payung Cultural Park.

This article was prepared by Ilmua Aminatuz Zuhriah, from the Merdeka Malang Tourism Diploma Program. With the title *"The Impact of Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, Ancillary on Tourist Visiting Interest in the Religious Tourism Destination of Gus Dur's Tomb, Jombang Regency."* This research is descriptive analysis, multiple linear regression, and hypothesis testing. The research results showed that the attraction and supporting variables had a partially significant effect on tourists' interest in visiting, while accessibility and amenities had a partially significant effect on tourists' visiting interest. The four independent variables have a simultaneous influence on tourists' interest in visiting, and in hypothesis testing it is known that attractiveness is the most dominant variable influencing tourists' interest in visiting the Gus Dur Tomb religious tourism in Jombang Regency. It can be concluded that when tourists are interested in visiting the Gus Dur Tomb religious tourism, what they most want is to see and enjoy the attractions.

The article was prepared by Elinda Anandar with the title *"Analysis of the Influence of Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, Ancillary on Interest in Visiting Tourists Through Loyalty Analysis of the Influence of Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, Ancillary on Interest in Visiting Tourists Through Loyalty Analysis of the Influence of Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, Ancillary on Interest Visiting Tourists Through Tourist Loyalty as a Mediating Variable"*. Through analysis and discussion, the results showed that Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, Ancillary had a positive and significant effect on Tourist Loyalty. Furthermore, Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, Ancillary have a positive and significant impact on visiting interest. These results show that what tourists get and feel has a positive impact, thereby making tourists interested in visiting San Terra De Laponte, Pujon, Malang Regency.

Result and Analysis

According to Mathieson and Wall, tourism includes a series of activities that involve the temporary movement of individuals or groups outside their domicile, as well as places that can meet the needs of visitors while at the destination. Yoeti also said that tourism is visitors who come for recreation and sightseeing. Religious tourism has an important role in strengthening the spiritual, cultural and social values of society. This activity is not only a means of getting closer to God through pilgrimages or religious rituals, but also introduces the richness of local culture rooted in religious traditions, such as the architecture of mosques, temples, churches or other holy sites. In addition, religious tourism can improve the economy of surrounding communities through supporting services, such as lodging, specialty culinary delights and souvenirs, while promoting inter-religious tolerance through cross-cultural experiences.

Solo's Sheikh Zayed Mosque, which was inaugurated as a symbol of bilateral relations between Indonesia and the United Arab Emirates, has become a significant religious tourism attraction. The majestic architectural beauty, combined with a strong Islamic feel, makes this mosque not only a place of worship, but also a popular tourist destination. Research on the influence of the 4A components (Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity, and Ancillary) is very relevant to understand what motivates tourists to visit this mosque.

Specifications of the Sheikh Zayed Solo Mosque

The Sheikh Zayed Solo Grand Mosque is one of the tourist attractions in Solo, specifically in Cinderejo, Gilingan Village, Banjarsari District. It was inaugurated on November 14 2022, which was attended directly by President Joko Widodo together with the President of the United Arab Emirates (PEA) Mohammad Bin Zayed Al Nahyan. The Sheikh Zayed Mosque is magnificent, creating awe for everyone who sees it. The Sheikh Zayed Mosque is often referred to as a replica of the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque, however it still displays Indonesian characteristics by displaying Kawung Batik in the mosque foyer, and integrated into the carpet on the main floor. So that it combines local culture with Arabic architectural style, as well as in the middle it is combined with a geometric design. The Sheikh Zayed Mosque has a large dome as high as 65 meters in its main building, then four towers as high as 75 meters. (Solopos.com 2023).

The Sheikh Zayed Mosque has a land area of 2.7 hectares. The Sheikh Zayed Mosque has a mosque area of 8,000 square meters with a maximum congregation capacity of 12,000 people. This mosque has a VIP room, a 20 square meter library and a basement used for men's and women's ablutions. As well as the establishment of an Islamic center around the mosque complex. So that later the Sheikh Zayed mosque will become an educational center such as the establishment of a TPA, Tafsir Al-Qur'an, Madrasah and economic sectors such as halal products which will be established at the Islamic Center. (mardira; 2023)

Tourists who come to the Sheikh Zayed Mosque from the general public, both Islamic and non-Islamic, are allowed to visit the Sheikh Zayed Mosque as long as they are dressed politely and wear a head covering. The average number of tourists visiting the Sheikh Zayed Mosque is around 10,000 tourists on weekdays, whereas if On weekends the number of visitors can triple, the number of visitors is very high and even reached a record in one month reaching 300,000 thousand visitors. Meanwhile, in 2023 alone, almost 3 million visitors will come to the Sheikh Zayed Mosque. (Results of an interview with the takmir of the Sheikh Zayed mosque).

The Sheikh Zayed Solo Mosque organizes various activities during the month of Ramadan which include Islamic studies, fasting together, and congregational worship. Some of these activities include tafsir studies, thematic studies after the Asr prayer, as well as preparation for fasting together (bukber). Apart from that, worship activities such as congregational Tarawih prayers are also part of this mosque's routine activities in the holy month. To support the smooth running of activities, the Sheikh Zayed Solo Mosque prepares 8-9 thousand portions of food and drinks every day, so as to create a solemn and togetherness Ramadan atmosphere for the congregation. (Interview Results)

The Sheikh Zayed Solo Grand Mosque implements a number of general rules that must be obeyed by the congregation in order to maintain comfort and order. These regulations include prohibitions on playing in the pool around the mosque, bringing food into the mosque area, bringing matches into the main hall, carrying sharp weapons, bringing pets, and bringing food or objects with strong odors. Apart from that, congregants are also prohibited from using toa because it can disturb the comfort of other congregants who are praying. This regulation was conveyed by Mas Riski, one of the takmirs of the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque in Solo.

Figure 1. the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque in

Interest in Tourist Visits

Interest in tourist visits is one of the important aspects in the tourism industry that influences the success of tourist destinations. With increasing interest in visits, the positive impact on the economy, culture and environment of local communities is increasingly felt. However, understanding what drives tourists to choose a destination is a challenge in itself.

According to Alvianna (2017) tourism interest is the interest of people who will travel to find out something unique in an area. Prospective consumers mean visitors who want to come to a tourist spot or who have already visited but want to come back to the tourist spot. There are many factors that influence interested tourists in choosing a destination, the factors determining interest in tourist visits are as follows:

1. Attraction

According to Nurdin (2019), Attraction is the most important product element because it is the core reason for visitors why they are willing to make sacrifices to visit a tourist destination. Attraction is the attractiveness of a place and is the main reason and motivation for visitors to visit a place.

According to Ningtias (2021) Attractions are a significant component in attracting tourist arrivals. Things that can be developed into tourist attractions are called tourism capital or resources. There are three main attractions that attract tourist arrivals, namely 1) Natural Resources such as mountains, lakes, beaches and hills; 2) cultural tourism attractions such as traditional house architecture in villages, archaeological sites, ritual arts and crafts, festivals, daily community life, hospitality, food; and 3) artificial attractions such as sporting events, shopping, exhibitions, conferences and others. Tourism capital can be developed into tourist attractions in places where tourist capital is found and outside its original location. According to Priambudi (2021) tourist attractions are divided into tourist attractions.

From the explanation about Attraction, it can be understood that attraction is the core performance of a tourist spot which makes tourists choose to visit that tourist spot, the indicator can be its natural beauty, the architecture of the buildings or works at that place, or the events presented by the tourist spot.

Inaugurated on November 14, 2022, Solo's Sheikh Zayed Mosque is a significant tourist attraction, renowned for its magnificent architecture and stunning design that seamlessly blends local Indonesian elements, such as kawung batik, with Arabic architectural styles. The main attraction also comes from the large dome as high as 65 meters and the minaret which rises as high as 75 meters, making it a replica of the Sheikh Zayed Grand Mosque with a distinctive Indonesian touch.

Figure 2. Area inside the mosque

2. Accessibility

According to Wanda and Pangestuti (2018) accessibility is the means and infrastructure to achieve a destination, for example, road access, traffic convenience and road direction are important aspects of a destination. Meanwhile, according to Nabila and Widiyastuti (2018) accessibility is the ease with which someone can achieve a goal which includes safety, comfort and travel time.

According to Cooper, accessibility consists of all the infrastructure and facilities needed by visitors to reach their destination, including public transportation accessibility, operational factors including service frequency and operating routes, airports, ports, railway lines, etc. According to (Wanda and Pangestuti; 2018) accessibility has a significant influence on the satisfaction of tourists who visit tourist attractions, because if the travel access is easy and the parking is comfortable, there will be potential for visitors to visit again.

According to (Faraby & Rozi; 2021) this accessibility is known as the convenience available at a tourist attraction which brings tourists to move from one place/region to another. The accessibility referred to here is such as roads, ports, etc. A place is considered a halal tourist attraction if its accessibility is adequate. There are two variable components. The first is access to information. Here visitors can get information related to halal/religious tourism. The second is affordability where tourist attractions are easy to visit. If you cover the accessibility aspects above, you will definitely feel satisfied at the tourist attractions you visit.

It can be understood from the statement above that actionability is the convenience for tourists to visit these tourist attractions. The indicators include facilities and infrastructure such as road access, both in terms of infrastructure and information, contributing directly to tourist satisfaction, increasing the potential for repeat visits, and making destinations more inclusive, including in the context of halal tourism.

This mosque is located in Cinderejo, Gilingan Village, Banjarsari District, Solo, and is easily accessible to general tourists, both Muslims and non-Muslims. Visitors can enter provided they dress modestly and cover their heads, and can access various facilities such as the VIP room and library. This good accessibility is reflected in the high number of visitors, reaching 10,000 people on weekdays and up to 30,000 people on weekends.

3. Amenity

According to Alvianna (2020) amenities are a series of facilities to meet tourists' needs in terms of accommodation, provision of food and drinks, entertainment venues, shopping and other services. According to Saway (2019) amenities are an attraction for tourists, but a lack of amenities will make tourists avoid certain destinations.

According to Nawangsar (2018) amenities are all things that can support accommodation (lodging), both from affordable accommodation, easy to access, then the needs of tourists while there, such as food and drinks that are guaranteed to be halal, entertainment and easy places to shop. . So that makes tourism comfortable. Because the better the amenities, the more comfortable the tourists will be.

Amenities are all forms of facilities that tourists need while carrying out tourist activities. This facility also determines the duration of a tourist's visit, so it is necessary to ensure that the facilities provided do not have any shortcomings so that tourists feel comfortable when visiting. Sugiama (2011) explained that while tourists are in a tourist destination, facilities consist of all types of supporting infrastructure and facilities such as accommodation, services, supporting food and drinks, performance buildings, entertainment venues and retail businesses.

According to Muharromah & Anwar (2020) amenities in a tourist attraction are said to be good in terms of several indicators, namely as follows:

- a. A restaurant, namely a tourist spot, must guarantee the halal, healthy, cleanliness of its food.
- b. Hospitality place to stay. Whether it is close to accommodation or not, whether access to accommodation or hotels is easy or not is an important indicator of amenities.

- c. Skincare spas, facial treatments, massages and other supporting places around tourist attractions are therefore included in amenities. The more places there are to serve tourists, the better tourism will be.
- d. Travel agency. There are main requirements that you need to know to become a tourism travel agency, namely adhering to providing tour packages that are in accordance with religious tourism, and travel agencies are required to provide a list of foods that are halal licensed, as well as providing recommendations for interesting food places.
- e. According to Muharromah & Anwar (2020), a tourist guide is someone whose job is to accompany tourists when visiting a tourist spot in a city/region. The requirements for becoming a sharia/religious tourist guide are that he is able to implement sharia values in the work he undertakes, is honest, has good morals, wears polite clothing in accordance with Islamic ethics and has equipment in accordance with specified professional standards.

So it can be understood from the explanation above that Amenities Overall, good quality amenities from infrastructure to services can increase comfort, duration of visit and attractiveness of the destination for tourists, especially in the context of religious or halal tourism. The indicators are the availability of amenities that are affordable, easily accessible and support tourist needs, such as halal food, entertainment and shopping, all of which increase tourist comfort.

Adequate facilities at the Sheikh Zayed Solo Mosque also contribute to the positive experience of visitors. Ample parking areas, clean toilets, modern ablution areas and disability-friendly access demonstrate attention to the needs of various types of tourists. Apart from that, the existence of halal food kiosks, Islamic souvenir shops, and children's play areas around the mosque provide added value for visitors who come with their families.

The Sheikh Zayed Mosque provides various facilities that support visitor comfort, such as ablution rooms for men and women, an underground room, and an Islamic Center which is expected to become an educational and economic center. This facility attracts visitors not only to worship, but also to access religious and social activities, such as tafsir studies, Madrasas, and halal products at the Islamic Center.

4. Ancillary

According to Pangestuti (2019) ancillary service is the availability of public facilities and facilities used by tourists which also support the implementation of tourist activities for example ancillary service such as ATM centers, hospitals, banks, money changers, and so on. Apart from that, ancillary service includes the existence of various organizations to facilitate and encourage the development and marketing of tourism at the destination in question.

According to Widyaningsih (2020) an ancillary is an agency that organizes tourist trips which includes tour guides, ticket reservations, travel agents, information centers and additional services that can make things easier for tourists. Because each tourist spot certainly has different additional services, the more complete the supporting services, the more comfortable the tourists will be.

According to Sugiana, ancillary is an additional service provided at tourist attractions that allows visitors to increase their sense of protection and security. Like an information center. The presence of complementary or ancillary services at a tourist destination contributes to the sustainability of that tourist destination.

By explaining ancillaries, it can be understood that with adequate ancillary service, tourist destinations can increase comfort, security and attractiveness for tourists, as well as support the sustainability of tourist attraction management. Indicators such as tourist guides, ATM centers, hospitals, banks, tourist security, such as information centers, which contribute to the sustainability of tourist destinations.

Good support services are also an important aspect in increasing interest in visits. Professional mosque management with friendly staff, knowledgeable tour guides, and the availability of tourist information via social media and official websites provide comfort and certainty for visitors. Collaborative programs with the government and local communities to organize large events also increase the attractiveness of mosques as religious tourism destinations.

Ancillary services such as routine activities during the month of Ramadan (Islamic studies, fasting together, and Tarawih prayers) also add to the attraction for visitors. This mosque also provides 8,000-9,000 portions of food and drinks every day to support community fasting activities. Rules implemented to maintain comfort, such as prohibitions on bringing food, sharp weapons, or pets, also contribute to a comfortable and orderly experience for the congregation.

Conclusion

The results of this research show that the influence of Attraction, Accessibility, Amenity and Ancillary factors is very large on the number of tourist visits to the Sheikh Zayed Mosque, Solo. The beauty of the architecture and design of the mosque (Attraction) which combines local cultural elements with Arabic architectural style is the main attraction that influences tourists' interest in visiting. Good accessibility, both in terms of strategic location and facilities that make it easier for visitors, also increases the number of visits, with easy access for Muslim and non-Muslim tourists.

The facilities provided by the Sheikh Zayed Mosque (Amenities), such as the ablution room, VIP room and Islamic Center, provide comfort and support religious and social activities for visitors. Apart from that, supporting services (Ancillary) such as Islamic study activities, fasting together, and congregational prayers during the month of Ramadan also increase visitors' interest in coming.

Overall, the relationship between these four factors is very close. Attraction attracts visitors' initial attention, while Accessibility, Amenity, and Ancillary play an important role in ensuring visitor comfort and satisfaction, which ultimately contributes to increasing the number of visits to the Sheikh Zayed Mosque Solo.

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